

Nonlinear effect analysis and compensation based on improved friction observer for torque rotating stage

ABSTRACT: In semiconductor precision packaging and other automation equipment alignment applications, the nonlinear motion caused by the structural characteristics and friction effect of the torque type rotating motion stage seriously affects the output accuracy and stability. To solve this problem, the motion characteristics of the rotating stage and the influence mechanism of friction nonlinearity on the accuracy are analyzed in detail. Besides, a compound control strategy based on the kinematics model and Stribeck friction model is designed. Meanwhile, a friction disturbance observer based on the output position feedback is improved for a simple parameter tuning. Finally, the experimental system is built to carry out validation tests, including nonlinear characteristic identification and comparison experiments of performance. The experimental results show that the linear tracking error of the torque type rotating stage is less than $1.47\ \mu\text{m}$ after adopting the designed model-based composite control (MBCC) strategy, and the dynamic rotary angle deviation is less than 0.0187° , and the linearity of output motion is increased to 97.57%, which verifies that the adopted analysis method and compensation strategy can effectively reduce the frictional nonlinearity and improve the motion accuracy, this method can also be used in other precision electromechanical systems.

KEYWORDS: Rotating stage, Mechanical analysis, Frictional nonlinear effect, Disturbance observation.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the post-Moore era, with the continuous development of precision machining manufacturing and automation technologies, there is a greater demand for micron and nanoscale components with miniaturization, high integration, and high interconnection. These technologies are currently widely used in the fields such as microelectronics, biomedicine, optics and nanomaterials¹⁻³. As we all know, the final quality of automation equipment is generally determined by the motion systems involved in the manufacturing process, especially the motional precision of mechanical actuators directly affects the product accuracy⁴. For example, in the latest MicroLED mass transfer applications, it is necessary to transfer an array of LED-chips with a size of about $30\ \mu\text{m}$ on the carrier to the bottom substrate in bulk, and the transfer alignment accuracy is required to be less than $\pm 1\ \mu\text{m}$ ⁵⁻⁷. However, in addition to the requirements for alignment accuracy, it is essential that the motion execution stage has a high carrying capacity and large stroke, which puts forward higher requirements for packaging accuracy and stroke simultaneously^{8,9}. Otherwise, the X/Y/ θ position deviation of the large-size chip carrier in the horizontal plane will seriously affect the alignment and interconnection quality.

At present, motion transfer and output components based on various types of motor drives occupy most of the alignment operations in precision automated production lines. However, due to the limitations of frictional nonlinear effects and assembly errors, etc, the final alignment accuracy of traditional mechanical direct-drive rotary motors is difficult to meet the current high-precision requirements¹⁰⁻¹². The influence of frictional nonlinearity on the accuracy of linear motion can be easily measured and compensated, but the friction analysis of mechanical rotary motion devices is more complicated because of the presence of intermediate transmission parts. More seriously, in a wide range of precision rotation operations, the influence of nonlinear motion on accuracy becomes

more significant with the increase of stroke. Therefore, how to solve the nonlinear problem of the mechanical motion stage under the condition of large-stroke motion has always been a key scientific problem in ensuring the precision of high-precision equipment.

In response to the friction problem in mechanical motion stage, some scholars have carried out research in this field. Boonsri et al.¹³ proposed an extended Kalman filter to estimate the friction of system based on the Coulomb and the Dahl friction models, which reduced the adverse effects of friction disturbance on the positioning accuracy of the system. Besides, Wang et al.¹⁴ discussed the friction disturbance based on Stribeck friction model, and a simple second-order linear ESO is designed to track and compensate discontinuous Stribeck Friction. Huang et al.¹⁵ used an adaptive friction compensation method based on the LuGre friction model to solve the friction problem in a highly nonlinear and coupled servo system. However, although the above studies have reduced the adverse effects of nonlinear factors such as friction on the motion system to a certain extent by mainly focused on optimizing the parameters and accuracy of the friction model¹⁶⁻¹⁸, it without further combining the dynamic driving characteristics and nonlinear transfer mechanisms of the mechanical system.

Therefore, in order to solve the nonlinear problem of the mechanical motion stage under the condition of large-stroke motion, this paper designs a torque rotating stage with large rotation range and high precision. And takes this stage as a typical example to analyze the nonlinear characteristics and the adverse effects of friction disturbances on the output precision in detail. Besides, the disturbance observation structure based on the friction model is improved, and a feedforward and feedback control strategy based on multiple models is established, and simulation verification is carried out. Finally, a prototype experimental system is built, and a series of performance tests are carried out. By comparing with the traditional proportional-integral-derivative (PID) control method, the ef-

fectiveness of the analysis method and model-based composite control (MBCC) adopted in this paper in solving the nonlinear motion problem of the rotating stage is verified.

II. ANALYSIS AND MODELING OF TORQUE TYPE SINGLE-DRIVE ROTATING STAGE

A. Mechanical structure and working principle of the rotating stage

Due to the influence of electromagnetic effects and mechanical nonlinear errors, direct-drive rotary motors suffer from problems such as poor low-speed stability and insufficient accuracy (usually higher than $\pm 30 \mu\text{rad}$)^{19,20}. In particular, in order to study the nonlinear motion characteristics and compensation methods of this rotating platform, a single-drive rotating stage is designed as a typical mechanical object for correlation analysis. This stage utilizing the displacement conversion of the lever-type transmission structure, and the rotation center of this stage is supported by a high-precision roller bearing, ensuring accurate and smooth rotation, as shown in Fig. 1(a).

Besides, a high-precision stepper motor is used to actuate a linear slider by a double-row cross roller guide rail, and the end of the linear slider contacts the right edge of the connecting block on the high-precision rotary bearing stage. In addition, on the left side of the stage, a preload spring provides initial pressure to ensure that the right side of the connecting block and the slider are always in a stable contact state during the rotation process. At the same time, in order to reduce the contact friction during the rotation process from the perspective of the mechanical structure, a ball joint is added to the contact area between the slider and the connecting plate to convert the sliding friction into rolling friction, thereby reducing the friction resistance at the contact point. Finally, the motion relationship of the torque type single-drive rotating stage is shown in Fig. 1(b).

When the stepper motor drives the linear slider to move forward, the slider generates torque after contacting the right edge of the connecting block, which in turn causes the connecting block to rotate around the center of the high-precision rotary bearing. The principle of generating rotary motion is shown in Fig. 1.

B. Kinematics and nonlinear effect analysis of the rotating stage

To analyze the relationship between the stepper motor input and the rotation displacement output of the rotating stage, the motion relationship model of the designed rotating stage is established. According to the analysis model in Fig. 1(b), the relationship between the input X_{in} caused by the stepper motor driving the slider and the output rotation angle θ of the turntable can be expressed as follows:

FIG. 1. Torque type rotating stage and its motion relationship. (a) mechanical structure diagram of torque type rotating stage, (b) motion relationship sketch.

$$\sin \theta = \frac{X_{in}}{L + \Delta L} \quad (1)$$

Where L is the distance from the contact point to the center of the rotating bearing, and ΔL is the displacement change of the contact point during the rotation process. As the rotation angle θ increases, the contact point undergoes a lateral displacement d . So, the positional deviation d can be expressed as follows:

$$\tan \theta = \frac{X_{in}}{L} \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta L = \frac{L(1 - \cos \theta)}{\cos \theta} \quad (3)$$

Combining the above formula, the rotation angle θ can be expressed as follows:

$$\theta = \arcsin \frac{X_{in}}{L + \Delta L} \quad (4)$$

According to Equation(4), it can be seen that the torque type rotating stage driven on one side has motion nonlinearity. As the rotation angle increases, the lateral offset d of the contact point also increases, which ultimately leads to a more significant output nonlinear effect. In addition, by conducting force analysis on the rotating stage and considering the influence of dynamic changes in contact points during the motion process, it can be concluded that:

$$F_s \cdot (L + \Delta L) + M_f = F_{in} \cdot (L + \Delta L) \quad (5)$$

Where M_f represents the friction torque contained in the mechanical rotating stage (mainly the friction resistance in the high-precision bearing). At present, the Stribeck model is based on the microstructure of the surface of the object and the essential principle of friction, and can well describe the transition process between static friction and dynamic friction. Parameters such as the static friction coefficient, dynamic friction coefficient and transition speed in the model can be adjusted according to the specific situation and are suitable for different practical scenarios. Therefore, the following Stribeck model is used to describe the friction torque^{21,22}, which can be expressed as follows:

When the angular velocity of the rotating stage satisfies $|\dot{\theta}(t)| < \alpha$, the static friction torque is expressed as follows:

$$M_f(t) = \begin{cases} M_s & M(t) > M_s \\ M(t) & -M_s < M_f < M_s \\ -M_s & M(t) < -M_s \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

While the angular velocity of the rotating stage satisfies $|\dot{\theta}(t)| > \alpha$:

$$M_f(t) = \left[M_c + (M_s - M_c)e^{-|\dot{\theta}(t)/v_s|^\delta} \right] \text{sgn}(v(t)) + bv(t) \quad (7)$$

Where M_s is the maximum static friction, M_c is the dynamic friction, V_s is the Stribeck speed, which is a speed threshold used to determine the area where friction drops rapidly, δ is the Stribeck index, which determines the rate of decrease of friction when the speed approaches zero, b is the friction component with a linear relationship with the viscous friction coefficient, and $\dot{\theta}$ is the relative speed.

As shown in Fig. 2(a), the relationship between the friction force and the rotation speed of the rotating stage shows that when the speed increases and enters the dynamic friction stage, the friction force exhibits a significant nonlinear effect. However, in the static friction stage, coulomb friction plays a major role, and the relationship between friction force and displacement can be considered linear, as shown in Fig. 2(b).

From the above analysis, the influence of friction on the accuracy of the mechanical turntable is mainly reflected in the nonlinear change of force caused by the stick-slip effect introduced by dynamic friction when the direction of motion changes, which in turn affects the force balance and acceleration stability of the turntable system. In particular, at low

FIG. 2. Comparison of motion characteristics in different friction stages. (a) stribeck friction model, (b) static friction model.

speeds, the low-speed creep phenomenon caused by friction also leads to output nonlinearity. Therefore, it is necessary to eliminate or compensate for the nonlinear motion effects introduced by the dynamic changes of the motion process and stick-slip friction as much as possible and carry out nonlinear compensation control to improve the accuracy and stability of the rotating stage.

III. CONTROL STRATEGY IMPROVEMENT AND SIMULATION OF THE MBCC

A. Model description of the rotating stage system

Based on the above analysis of the friction of the rotating stage, considering the influence of the mechanical friction of the moving parts, the dynamic model of the moving stage can be expressed as follows:

$$J\ddot{\theta}(t) + C\dot{\theta} + K_s(\theta) = u - M_f(\dot{\theta}) \quad (8)$$

Where J represents the moment of inertia of the output end of the rotating stage, C is the system damping, K_s is the preload force of the spring in the rotating stage, which is regarded as the internal force of the system here, u is the control input of the rotating stage, and M_f is the friction torque caused by friction resistance.

According to the dynamic model of the rotating stage determined by the formula (8), it can be assumed that the position and speed states of the designed mechanical turntable are respectively $x = [x_1, x_2]^T = [\theta, \dot{\theta}]^T$. Substituting the friction model into the mechanical system model of the rotating stage, while ignoring the damping of the mechanical system, combined with equations (6) and (8), the state equation of the rotating system can be combined as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}_1 = x_2 \\ J\dot{x}_2 = u - M_f(t) \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

If the limit spring force K_s in the above equation is also treated as an internal term of the mechanical system, and the friction torque M_f is treated as an external disturbance of the system, the disturbance observer (DOB) approach can be used to approximate and compensate for the friction force, thereby eliminating the influence of friction nonlinearity on the accuracy of the rotating stage.

B. Improved of the disturbance observer based on position signal of rotating stage

In a mechanical rotating stage, disturbances mainly affect the output accuracy of the rotation angle in the form of frictional force or torque. Considering the sensor installation position and measurement convenience, a position-based observer is designed specifically based on the angle as the direct output measurement value. According to the idea of eliminating disturbances by the disturbance observer²³, the control block diagram of the traditional disturbance observer shown in Fig. 3(a) can be obtained. The transfer function from disturbance to output can be expressed as:

$$G_{dy} = \frac{G_p(s)G_n(s)[1 - Q(s)]}{G_p(s) + Q(s)[G_p(s) - G_n(s)]} \quad (10)$$

Usually, to improve the observation effect of low-frequency disturbances and the convergence speed, $Q(s)$ is often designed as a low-pass filter, then:

$$\lim_{w \rightarrow 0} G_{dy}(jw) = 0 \quad (11)$$

Furthermore, it can achieve suppression of input disturbances. However, the accuracy and feasibility of the nominal inverse model directly affect the effect of the observer, and the order and parameter design of the filter $Q(s)$ are particularly important. In addition, G_n has unavoidable model errors, and the nominal inverse model of G_p is usually difficult to implement physically, so it must be jointly designed in conjunction with $Q(s)$. Therefore, the rationality of the parameter and order design of the filter $Q(s)$ will directly affect the observer effect.

To solve the above problems, based on the idea of an expansion state, the friction disturbance of the rotating stage during its motion is regarded as a new state $x = [x_1, x_2, d]^T =$

$[\theta, \dot{\theta}, M_f]^T$, that is, the state equation of equation (9) is rewritten as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x}_1 \\ \dot{x}_2 \\ \dot{d} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1/J \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ d \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1/J \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} u \quad (12)$$

$$y = [1 \ 0 \ 0] \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ d \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

Assume that the rewritten observer gain is $L = [l_1, l_2]^T$, and the coefficient matrix of the observer equation can be expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} \hat{A} = \begin{bmatrix} -l_1 & -1/J \\ -l_2 & 0 \end{bmatrix} & \hat{B} = \begin{bmatrix} -l_1^2 - l_2/J \\ -l_1 l_2 \end{bmatrix} \\ \hat{C} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} & \hat{D} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ l_1 \\ l_2 \end{bmatrix} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Furthermore, the characteristic equation of the observer can be obtained as:

$$\det(sI - \hat{A}) = s^2 + sl_1 - l_2/J \quad (15)$$

Let $l_1 = g_1$, $-l_2/J = g_2$, when the characteristic equation pole is selected in the left-half plane, the observer meets the stability criterion. And the state equation form of the above observer is expressed in the form of transfer function, that is, the observer structure shown in Fig. 3(b) can be equivalent to the form of Fig. 3(c), at this time, the S^2 term in the nominal model has been equivalently eliminated. Through the improved observer and the position of the characteristic roots, the frictional disturbance can be estimated effectively, and get new control input $e = u_f - d$. After adopting this method, the parameter design of the disturbance observer is easier to implement and adjust.

C. Design and simulation of the MBCC strategy

Finally, combining all the above kinematic models and observer models, we get the feedforward and feedback control structure shown in Fig. 3(d). Among them, the kinematic inverse solution of the feedforward link is mainly used to adjust the input signal trajectory, eliminate the nonlinearity of the rotation output caused by the unilateral torque drive structure, and convert the linear displacement output by the linear drive module into the expected input angle, to directly make a difference with the output angle of the rotating stage to form the corresponding feedback, that is:

$$\theta_{in} = f(x_{in}, L, \Delta l) \quad (16)$$

FIG. 3. Different control block diagrams for disturbance. (a) common disturbance observer control structure, (b) structure of disturbance observer based on position feedback, (c) optimization of method (b), (d) feedforward and feedback composite control diagram.

$$e_1 = \theta_m - \theta \quad (17)$$

In addition, the friction disturbance of the rotating stage is regarded as the external disturbance of the ideal model of the turntable system. The designed observer outputs the observed value d of the disturbance and uses it as the feedforward in the inner loop of the turntable system to compensate for the friction. The input signal of the turntable system can be expressed as:

$$u = M_f + G(s)e_1 - \hat{M}_f \quad (18)$$

It can be seen that when $M_f \approx \hat{M}_f$, the friction disturbance value is basically effectively acquired and compensated by the observer.

To verify the effectiveness of the designed control strategy, a corresponding control simulation system is built in MATLAB Simulink. Based on the above dynamic model and for the convenience of simulation implementation, the designed rotating stage is approximated as a commonly used second-order mechanical system. The input signal of the system is $0.1 \times \sin(2\pi t)$, and the sampling time is set to 0.001s. Finally, the constructed Simulink simulation control framework is shown in Fig. 4.

In addition, to illustrate the tracking performance of the designed control strategy, a comparative simulation based on the commonly used PID control strategy is added. The parameters of each module are designed as follows:

1. Control strategy adopted: According to the Stribeck model used in the previous article, the simulation preliminarily sets $F_c=15\text{N}$, $F_s=20\text{N}$, $V_s=1$, $b=2$. The other relevant parameters are set as follows: $m=0.2\text{Kg}$, $J=235.73\text{Kg}\cdot\text{mm}^2$, $g_1=300$, $g_2=27000$.
2. PID control strategy: to compare the performance of the rotating stage under different control strategies, the tracking effect under the PID control strategy is tested under the same operating conditions. The PID parameters after adjustment are as follows: $K_p=2000$, $K_i=2$, $K_d=50$.

The upper part of Fig. 6 adopts the PID control strategy. The tracking effect of the output displacement of the rotating stage output end under the sinusoidal signal input is shown in Fig. 5(a) and (b), and the tracking error is about $\pm 1.2 \mu\text{m}$. In contrast, the lower part of Fig. 6 adds a disturbance observer based on the friction model to the feedback loop to observe and compensate for the friction nonlinearity that is difficult to measure. The corresponding tracking effect is shown in Fig. 5(c) and (d). Obviously, after the observer compensation, the bilateral tracking error of the rotating stage output end is significantly reduced, and the simulation error is less than $\pm 0.8 \mu\text{m}$.

In addition, the observation value based on the adopted friction model is shown in Fig. 6. It can be seen that the observer can accurately equalize the friction disturbance. Therefore, from the simulation effect, the proposed observer based on the friction model can effectively compensate for the friction disturbance, and compared with the traditional PID control strategy, this method has better tracking accuracy.

FIG. 4. Simulation block diagram in MATLAB Simulink.

FIG. 5. Comparison of sinusoidal tracking effect under different control strategies. (a) sinusoidal tracking curve under PID method, (b) position errors under PID method, (c) sinusoidal tracking curve under DOB method, (d) position errors under DOB method.

IV. ESTABLISHMENT AND TEST OF THE EXPERIMENTAL SYSTEM

A. Experimental system setup of the rotating stage

According to the torque rotating stage designed in Fig. 1, a high-precision stepper motor with displacement feedback,

a precision linear guide module (HIWIN-MGW7C1R50), a high-precision cross roller bearing (RU42, EFANT), and a spring preload device are used to form a rotating stage mechanical test system. The stepper motor (SL-2236A) is actuated through a driver and a control card (GCS800A). At the same time, a laser displacement sensor (PicoScale, SmarAct)

FIG. 6. The observation effect of the designed observer on Stribeck friction force.

and linear capacitive displacement (NS-DCS14, SYMC) with a feedback signal are used to measure the output displacement of the rotating stage, and then the corresponding rotation angle output under the linear displacement is obtained by using the turntable structure size relationship. Finally, an experimental verification system as shown in Fig. 7 is built. A series of performance test under different control strategies are carried out.

FIG. 7. The experiment system of the designed rotating stage.

B. Parameter identification of the rotating stage

To establish a disturbance compensation control strategy based on the friction model, it is necessary to identify the friction model parameters used in the control strategy. According to equation (7), the friction parameters that need to be identified are mainly M_c , M_s , b , and V_s . It should be pointed

out that in the constructed rotating stage test system, the reverse preload generated by the spring is regarded as an internal force. Therefore, the external motion resistance of the rotating stage system is mainly friction. Combined with the analysis of the influence mechanism of friction on stage motion in the previous article, by testing the output characteristics under constant speed motion, the corresponding Stribeck curve can be obtained, and then the corresponding friction parameters can be obtained based on the curve fitting.

When the rotating stage moves at a uniform speed at multiple different speeds, satisfying $F_{in} = F_f$, a set of corresponding control input signals and friction torque can be obtained. Then, the MATLAB curve fitting toolbox is used to obtain the fitting curve corresponding to the experimental measurement points, thereby obtaining the Stribeck friction curve of the constructed experimental system, as shown in Fig. 8(a).

By comparing the coefficients in equation (7) and correcting the curve, the required friction model parameters are obtained, and the remaining calculated parameters are listed together. Finally, the physical parameters of the rotating stage are obtained as shown in Table. I.

TABLE I. System parameters of the rotating stage.

Model parameter	Identification result
M_s	0.4613
V_s	0.0708
m	0.18 Kg
M_c	0.2032
b	0.0821
J	235.73 Kg·mm ²

C. Compensation performance test of the nonlinear effect

Based on the composite control strategy designed and verified by simulation in the previous article and combined with the physical parameters of the rotating stage experimental system obtained by identification, the corresponding performance test experiment is carried out. First, the PID control strategy in the previous chapter is used to directly test the tracking effect of the ramp signal trajectory at different speeds, and the displacement sensor is used to measure the linear displacement of the output end. The test result curve is shown in Fig. 8(b).

It can be clearly seen from the test results that the rotating stage has obvious nonlinear motion effects under the PID control strategy. The displacement deviation caused by the displacement nonlinearity at the output end is as high as 100 μ m, resulting in a serious decrease in motion accuracy.

In addition, the output error caused by friction and the nonlinear characteristics of the rotating stage is tested at slow and high speeds, as shown in Fig. 9. It can be seen that at low speeds (in Fig. 9(a)), the creep and vibration caused by friction are more significant (in Fig. 9(b)).

Then, based on the composite control strategy of kinematic

FIG. 8. Nonlinear characteristic test experiments of the rotating stage. (a) identification curve of friction model, (b) output nonlinear tests at different speeds.

feedforward and friction compensation feedback designed in the previous article, combined with the established kinematic inverse relationship and friction identification and compensation model, the trajectory tracking effect under the same conditions is tested. When the input stroke is about 2 mm, the corresponding turntable rotation angle under the linear output displacement is measured at the output end of the rotating stage (conversion relationship: $\theta = \arctan(X_{in}/L)$). The experimental results are shown in Fig. 10.

After adopting the composite control strategy of feedforward and DOB, the maximum linear error in dynamic motion is $1.47 \mu\text{m}$, and the corresponding rotation angle error is 0.0187° , while the dynamic error under the PID control strategy is $5.86 \mu\text{m}$ and 0.0742° .

D. Analysis and evaluation of the results

The motion performance of the rotating stage under different control strategies is tested, and the results are shown in Table. II. It can be seen that, the nonlinear effect of friction is more significant at low speed in actual experiment system, and the nonlinear effect caused by friction is more significant

FIG. 9. The output displacement error caused by friction at different speeds. (a) at a speed of 0.15mm/s, (b) at a speed of 5mm/s.

at the moment of stage startup and reversal, which is consistent with the change of the friction nonlinear curve obtained by identification. Besides, the kinematic inverse model is in-

FIG. 10. Trajectory tracking test of rotating stage under different control strategies.

TABLE II. System parameters of the rotating stage.

Methods	Position error in simulation	Position error in test	Angle error	Output linearity
PID	$\pm 1.2\mu\text{m}$	$5.86\mu\text{m}$	0.0742°	90.40%
MBCC strategy	$\pm 0.8\mu\text{m}$	$1.47\mu\text{m}$	0.0187°	97.59%

roduced to correct the input signal with change of stroke. The improved DOB based on the position and friction model can effectively suppress the influence of disturbance, which can ultimately improve the linearity and accuracy of the stage.

V. CONCLUSION

Aiming at the output nonlinear problem due to mechanical structural and motion friction in the torque rotating stage, this study analyzes the mechanism of nonlinear motion characteristic on the output precision in detail, and adopts a improved model-based control strategy to compensate it. The main contributions of this paper are as follows:

(1) the generation mechanism of nonlinear motion in a rotating stage is analyzed from the perspective of mechanical structure and friction characteristics, and the corresponding kinematic model is established;

(2) the DOB based on position feedback is optimized and validated, and a model-based composite control (MBCC) strategy is obtained to compensate the nonlinearity of the rotating stage;

(3) after adopting the MBCC strategy and identified friction model of the rotating stage, the linear tracking error of the rotating stage decreases to within $1.47\mu\text{m}$, and the precision of rotating motion can reach 0.0187° . Meanwhile, compared with the traditional PID strategy, the output displacement linearity is improved to 97.59%.

In summary, taking a torque rotating stage as an example, a nonlinear analysis method based on structural characteristics is established, and the feasibility and effectiveness of the adopted method to compensate for nonlinear motion arising from friction and mechanical structure are verified.

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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REFERENCE

- Pan, Z., Guo, C., Wang, X., Liu, J., Cao, R. Wafer-scale micro-LEDs transferred onto an adhesive film for planar and flexible displays. *Adv. Mater. Technol* 2020;5:2000549. <https://doi.org/10.1002/admt.202000549>, 2020..
- He, S., Tang, H., Zhang, K., Chen, C., Wang, J., Zhu, Z., Jian, G., Cui, C., and Chen, X. A flip-chip alignment system with the property of deviation self-correction at the nanoscale. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics* 2020;68:2345-2355. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2020.2973882>, 2020.
- Chen, Y., Xie, W., Tu, K., and Liu, Y. Fast and accurate alignment and bonding system based on advanced packaging technology. 2023 IEEE International Conference on Integrated Circuits, Technologies and Applications October. Hefei: 2023. pp.27-29. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICTA60488.2023.10364268>, 2023.
- Xiaopeng Yang, Menglun Zhang; Review of flexible microelectromechanical system sensors and devices. *Nanotechnol. Precis. Eng.* 1 June 2021; 4 (2): 025001. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.50004301>.
- Chen, F., Bian, J., Hu, J., Sun, N., Yang, B., Ling, H., Yu, H., Wang, K., Gai, M., Ma Y., and Huang, Y. Mass transfer techniques for large-scale and high-density microLED arrays. *Journal of Extreme manufacturing* 2022;4:042005. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2631-7990/ac92ee>, 2022.
- Jia, Y., Tang, H., Xu, S., Xu, Y., Chen, X., and Tian, Y. A novel decoupled flexure nanopositioner with thermal distortion self-elimination function. *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics* 2022;27:2953-2962. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMECH.2021.3127963>, 2022.
- Martin, Y., Nah, J., Kamlapurkar, S., Engelmann, S., and Barwicz, T. Toward high-yield 3D self-alignment of flip-chip assemblies via solder surface tension. 2016 IEEE 66th Electronic Components and Technology Conference May. Las Vegas: 2016. pp.588-594. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ECTC.2016.239>, 2016.
- Wu, Z., Tang, H., Feng, Z., Wang, W., He, S., Gao, J., Chen, X., He, Y., and Chen, X. A novel self-feedback intelligent vision measure for fast and accurate alignment in flip-chip packaging. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics* 2019;16:1776-1787. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TII.2019.2930078>, 2020.
- Lufan Zhang, Pengqi Zhang, Boshi Jiang, Heng Yan; Research trends in methods for controlling macro-micro motion platforms. *Nanotechnol. Precis. Eng.* 1 September 2023; 6(3):035001. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.50019384>.
- She, H., Zhang, H., and Xun, Q. Design and analysis of a new rotary precision micropositioning stage. 2016 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Biomimetics; Qingdao: 2016. pp.1554-1557. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ROBIO.2016.7866548>, 2016.
- Peng, Y., Sakurai, Y., Arai, Y., Shimizu, Y., and Gao, W. Design of a linear-rotary micro-stage. *Proceedings of SPIE - The International Society for Optical Engineering* 2011;8321:1-7. <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.904884>, 2011.

- ¹²Xun, Q. Design of a large-range compliant rotary micropositioning stage with angle and torque sensing. *IEEE Sensors Journal* 2014;15:2419-2430. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSEN.2014.2377779>, 2014.
- ¹³Kaewkham-ai, B., and Uthaichana, K. Comparative study on friction compensation using coulomb and dahl models with extended and unscented kalman filters. 2012 7th IEEE Conference on Industrial Electronics and Applications. Singapore: 2012. pp.191-195. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIEA.2012.6360721>, 2012.
- ¹⁴Wang, L., Li, Q., Jiao, R., Yin, Y., Feng, Y., and Liu, Y. Tracking of stiction friction based on second-order linear extended state observer. 2016 Chinese Control and Decision Conference. Yinchuan: 2016. pp.4334-4337. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CCDC.2016.7531746>, 2016.
- ¹⁵Huang, J., Zhang, X., Wang, G., Song, Z., and Yang, T. Adaptive friction compensation of electromechanical servo system based on LuGre model. 2018 13th IEEE Conference on Industrial Electronics and Applications. Wuhan: 2018. pp.2596-2600. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIEA.2018.8398149>, 2018.
- ¹⁶Huang, S., Liang, W., and Tan, K. K. Intelligent friction compensation: A review. *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics* 2019;24:1763-1774. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMECH.2019.2916665>, 2019.
- ¹⁷Lee, W., Lee, C. -Y., Jeong, Y. H., and Min, B. -K. Friction compensation controller for load varying machine tool feed drive. *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture* 2015;96?:47-54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmactools.2015.06.001>, 2015.
- ¹⁸Tao Huang, Yingbin Wang, Zhihong Luo, Huajun Cao, Guibao Tao, Mingxiang Ling; Feedback linearization and equivalent-disturbance compensation control strategy for piezoelectric stage. *Nanotechnol. Precis. Eng.* 1 May 2024;7(2):023006. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.50024700>.
- ¹⁹Ironless rotary motor- Akribis: <https://akribis-sys.com/products/rotary-stages/axm-series>, last access: 2 June 2024.
- ²⁰Lu, K. Y., Rasmussen, P. O., and Ritchie, E. Design considerations of permanent magnet transverse flux machines. *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics* 2011;47:2804-2807. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMAG.2011.2146758>, 2011.
- ²¹Liu, Y., Li, J., Zhang, Z. Hu, H., and Zhang, W. Experimental comparison of five friction models on the same test-bed of the micro stick-slip motion system. *Mechanical Sciences* 2015;6:15-28. <https://doi.org/10.5194/ms-6-15-2015>, 2015.
- ²²Chen, D., Yao, F., and Chai, S. Sliding mode control with observer for PMSM based on stiction friction model. 2014 Seventh International Symposium on Computational Intelligence and Design. Hangzhou: 2014. pp.469-472. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISCID.2014.216>, 2014.
- ²³Chen, W.H., Ballance, D. J., Gawthrop, P. J., and O'Reilly, J. A nonlinear disturbance observer for robotic manipulators. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics* 2000;47:932-938. <https://doi.org/10.1109/41.857974>, 2000.